

Sugar and Vitamin C Contents of Some Selected Fruits in Nigeria

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Abstract

Freshly plucked fruits are rich sources of several nutrients including vitamin C (ascorbic acid) and sugar. However, not all fruits have high contents of these nutrients. The ascorbic acid and reducing sugar contents of ten selected fruits (watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*), apple (*Malus domestica*), orange (*Citrus sinensis*), guava (*Psidium guajava*), coconut (*Cocos nucifera*), cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*), avocado (*Persea americana*), pawpaw (*Carica papaya*), pineapple (*Ananas comosus*), and banana (*Musa paradisiaca*)) fruits were determined using titrimetric method. The experimental results indicated that the total amount of reducing sugars in pineapple fruit was the highest value at 8.90% followed by coconut at 7.40%. The contents of vitamin C in the fruits varied significantly: the highest value was observed in the pawpaw fruit (22 mg/100g) and this was followed by the guava fruit (21mg/100g). Pineapple, orange, watermelon, avocado, coconut, banana, apple and cucumber were 14.10, 13.73, 7.05, 7.05, 6.15, 5.48, 5.25 and 4.95 mg/100g of vitamin C respectively. Banana, orange, pawpaw, watermelon, guava, apple, avocado, cucumber had sugar contents of 6.10, 5.20, 5.00, 4.80, 4.60, 4.40, 3.90, 3.50 parts/10g.

Keywords: Local Nigerian Fruits; Nutrient; Diet; Ascorbic acid; Fruit sugar.

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Fruits are major important components of the diet needed to maintain a healthy living. They are a vital part of modern healthy diet in several communities due to their taste, invigorating benefits and nutritional supplements (Hossain *et al.*, 2012; Ndife *et al.*, 2013). Fruits are a sub-set of vegetables and it refers to the part of the seed enclosed by a matured ovary (Nweze *et al.*, 2015). They are the means through which plants disseminate seeds. Fruits are significant in human nutrition because they contain low fat and calories, but have high contents of minerals, dietary fiber, and vitamins. Thus, they are important vitamin

sources including vitamin A (retinol), vitamin B1 (thiamine), vitamin B3 (niacin), vitamin B6 (pyridoxine), vitamin B9 (folate), vitamin C (ascorbic acid), and vitamin E (alpha-tocopherol), as well as minerals and dietary fiber (Wargovich, 2000). Varieties of fruits are available for consumption in Nigeria during the different seasons; these include grapes, oranges, apples, pawpaw, and pineapple. These are major sources of fibers, minerals, vitamins, and antioxidants necessary for maintaining proper human health (Jasmine, 2012).

Good human health has been correlated with fruit-rich-diets. In fact, fruit-rich-diets has been reported to lower the risk of some

types of cancers and cardiovascular disease, as well as reduce body mass index (Temple and Gladwin, 2003; Charlton *et al.*, 2003). Thus to prevent of chronic diseases including diabetes, heart diseases, obesity, and cancer, a nutrient goal was set by a recent WHO/FAO report on diet and nutrition which recommends intake of 400g (minimum) of fruits per day. Fruits generally contain carbohydrates in the form of sugars such as fructose, glucose, and lactose (Wilson *et al.*, 2015). Thus, whether ingested as a whole or in the form of liquid (juice), they have a hydrating effect, in addition to its numerous nutrients. Due to several positive effects associated with fruit consumption, researchers have focused on determining the contents of each nutrient of various fruits in various parts of the world (Hossain *et al.*, 2012; Ndife *et al.*, 2013). Fruits grown under different climatic and soil variations may vary in colour, taste, size, and ultimately nutrients contents. Thus, it is vital to determine the selected nutrients contents of some locally grown fruits.

In this study, the contents of two nutrients in the selected fruits were determined: vitamin C (ascorbic acid) and reducing sugars. Vitamin C is an important water-soluble vitamin that can be obtained from some natural foods, or it may be added to meals as a dietary supplement (Sani *et al.*, 2015). Since, humans cannot synthesize vitamin C; it is taken as an essential dietary component. It acts as a vital physiological anti-oxidant and as precursor molecule for other vital molecules, including vitamin E. Vitamin C is important for immune function and it helps in non-heme iron (plant-based iron) absorption. It's deficiency in humans has been linked to scurvy with symptoms such as fatigue, weakness, and capillary fragility (Wang and Still, 2007). Fruit-based sugars contents vary depending on the fruit type and the environmental conditions during growth and fruiting. Most fruits contain fructose with enormous variation in the contents of other sugars such as glucose, sucrose, and sorbitol (Jasmine, 2012). Glucose is the primary energy of the brain

and it is needed in muscle. In the present study, the vitamin C (ascorbic acid) contents and reducing sugars in ten selected fresh fruits obtained from local markets in Abraka town (Nigeria) were determined.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials, samples collection, and preparation

Analytical grade reagents were employed throughout this study. For sugar analysis, the

$$\% \text{Reducing sugar} = \frac{0.025v_1v_2}{v_3W} \times 100 \dots\dots(1)$$

reagents include Fehling's solutions A and solution B, neutral acetate solution (20%), potassium oxalate solution (10%), and methylene blue (1%) indicator. For vitamin C analysis, the chemicals include iodine solution (0.005 mol/L), starch indicator solution (1%), vitamin C stock solution (1000 mg/L) prepared by dissolving 100 mg of ascorbic acid in volumetric flask (100 mL). Ten different fresh fruits used for this study were obtained from fruit shops in Abraka, Nigeria. The fruits were identified in the herbarium of the Botany Department, Delta State University, Abraka. The fruits are watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*), apple (*Malus domestica*), orange (*Citrus sinensis*), guava (*Psidium guajava*), coconut (*Cocos nucifera*), cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*), avocado (*Persea americana*), pawpaw (*Carica papaya*), pineapple (*Ananas comosus*), and banana (*Musa paradisiaca*). The fruits were washed separately, seeds or pericarp were removed where needed, samples were cut into small pieces before separately freeze-drying in a Millorock Bench-Top freeze-dryer, and pulverizing using the Model 4 Thomas-Wiley laboratory mill. The samples were stored at -20 °C before the analysis.

2.2 Extraction and determination of vitamin C in each fruit

A 100 g mass of each pulverized sample was macerated by suspending for 48 h in n-hexane (800 mL) with intermittent shaking

(Najwa and Azrina, 2017). The extract was filtered through cotton wool and then No. 1 filter paper (Whatman). A rotary evaporator was used to concentrate the extract at 40 °C before drying at 35 °C in a water bath. The extracts were stored at 2-4 °C before the vitamin C analysis. For the vitamin C analysis of each fruit, the extract was mixed in distilled water (20 mL), before making up to 100 mL. Prior to titration of this sample, 20 mL was mixed with distilled water (150 mL) and starch indicator (1 mL), and then titrated against the iodine solution to the endpoint identified as the first permanent dark blue-black colour due to the starch-iodine complex. Each analysis was carried in triplicate per sample. The standard vitamin C solution (25 mL) was also titrated accordingly and the titre values recorded. These were used to calculate the concentration of vitamin C per 100g sample.

2.3 Determination of reducing sugars in each fruit

This method is similar to that reported by Jhaunmeer-Laulloo *et al.* (2003). Ten (10) g of the pulverized sample was added to distilled water (100 mL) (in 500 mL volumetric flask) and this was titrated to neutrality as indicated by the phenolphthalein endpoint. This was followed by addition of neutral lead acetate solution (10 mL), shaking and allowing to stand (10 min) before the addition of potassium oxalate solution in drops until no more precipitation. The flask was made up to mark, mixed, filtered, and some of the filtrate transferred into a burette (50 mL). The titration procedure was carried out using Fehling A and B solutions (5 mL each) in 250 mL conical flask mixed with water (10 mL) and some glass beads. While warming this solution, 5 mL of the sugar solution was added before adding methylene blue indicator (3 drops). The drop-wise addition of sugar solution was continued until a brick-red endpoint. This titration was carried out thrice but for each of these, the initial volume of sugars added were 2 mL less than the initial titre before adding methylene blue. The percentage reducing sugar per sample

was calculated using Eqn.1 where W is sample weight, v_2 is the dilution volume of the sample and v_3 is the average titre value. Data obtained were expressed as mean and standard deviation of triplicate determinations calculated using Microsoft Excel (2016).

3.0 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results obtained from the analysis of different fruits for their vitamin C and percentage reducing sugars contents are presented Table 1 and Fig. 1. The percentage reducing sugars (Fig 1a and Table 1) of these fruits ranged from 3.5 to 8.9 %. It was observed that pineapple fruit exhibited the highest percentage of reducing sugars of 8.9 %, followed by coconut and banana at 7.4 and 6.1 %, respectively. The percentage reducing sugars of other fruits ranged between 3.5 % for cucumber and 5.2 % for orange. On the other hand, the vitamin C contents of these fruits in mg/100g showed significantly varied values, with the highest recorded for pawpaw fruit at 22.05 mg/100g. This was followed by the guava fruit at 21.15 mg/100g, while the values for others fruits ranged from low in cucumber at 4.95 mg/100g to high for orange at 13.73 mg/100g.

In plants, fruits are major sugar-rich edible portions. It contains fructose, D-glucose, and sucrose in addition to several minerals, vitamins, and phytochemicals in varying percentages contingent on the fruit maturity and ripeness (Gidado *et al.*, 2018). Glucose is a high glycemic index substance which if consumed in fruits can either positively or negatively affect the glycemic status of an individual depending on the energy requirement. Of the ten fruits analyzed, pineapple was exhibited the highest content of sugar, while cucumber had the lowest. Apart from serving as energy sources, certain sugars are required for vital functions in the human body. For instance, ribose is a pentose sugar which enhances myocardial or skeletal muscle ATP levels recovery following highly-intensity exercise or ischemia (Aremu *et al.*, 2021). There are

proofs that supplemental ribose could prevent muscle fatigue in genetic disorders that hamper adequate energy production in the body (Qi, 2023), as well as provide extra energy to the heart. Lactose sugar appears to enhance calcium retention in children (Krog-Mikkelsen et al., 2011) and this type of dietary carbohydrate has an effect on the level of serum cholesterol, leading to lower concentrations when complex carbohydrates are consumed in the form of dietary fibre and pectin in preference to sucrose (Adeyeye

et al., 2020). These nutritional advantages notwithstanding, consumption of sugar-rich foods rich such as fructose sugar may lead to high triglycerides (hyper-triglyceridemia) and obesity (Chahopadhyay et al., 2014). It was observed that the fruits in the present study possess varied percentages of sugar. The concentration of sugar in these fruits can be attributed to different factors such as fruit type, formation of fruits as well as preservation and packaging.

Figure 1. Graphical representation of the (a) Reducing sugar, and (b) ascorbic acid data

Table 1. Percentage reducing sugar and vitamin C contents of selected fruit samples

Fruit	Reducing Sugar (% weight) per 10 g*	Ascorbic Acid content (mg/100 g)
Orange	5.20±0.10	13.73±0.43
Watermelon	4.80±0.26	7.05±0.26
Coconut	7.40±0.30	6.15±0.52
Guava	4.60±0.26	21.15±0.30
Pineapple	8.90±0.26	14.10±0.17
Banana	6.10±0.40	5.48±0.65
Pawpaw	5.00±0.30	22.05±0.36
Apple	4.40±0.26	5.25±0.26
Cucumber	3.50±0.26	4.95±0.17
Avocado	3.90±0.20	7.05±0.30

The vitamin C recommended daily allowance (RDA) for in adult is 60 mg (WHO, 2003). The contents of vitamin C in all the plants reported in this study (Fig 1b; Table 1) were lower than the required daily intake if fruits were the only intake source. Thus, it is recommended that more of these fruits should be consume in order to meet the RDA if fruits were the only vitamin C source. The content of vitamin C obtained for watermelon in this study 7.05 mg/100ml was lower than some reported in literature: 26.42 mg/100g by Okiei *et al.* (2009). This variation, as well as similar variation for other fruits, may be attributed to factors that affect ascorbic acid levels in the fruits which include climatic conditions such as light, temperature, and the amounts of nitrogen fertilizer during the growing stage of the crop (Wilson *et al.*, 2015).

4.0 CONCLUSION

The ascorbic acid and reducing sugar contents of ten selected fruits (orange, apple, pineapple, guava, avocado, coconut, cucumber, watermelon, banana, and pawpaw) fruits were determined. The results showed that the all the fruits contained both nutrients: for the total reducing sugar, pineapple had the highest percentage at 8.9 % followed by coconut at 7.4 %. The contents of vitamin C of the fruits varied significantly with the highest recorded in the pawpaw fruit with 22 mg/100g, followed by guava fruit with 21 mg/100g. It may be concluded that pawpaw, guava, pineapple and orange exhibited the highest concentration of vitamin C, while the pineapple fruit, coconut, and banana were the highest in terms of reducing sugar. These fruits could serve as adequate source of energy but if they are the only vitamin C sources for an individual, it is recommended that sufficient amount be consumed to meet the RDA.

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7.0 CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors have no relevant financial or non financial interest to disclose.

8.0 AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTIONS

Odagwe, Alexander A.: Writing–original draft/review and editing, Data curation, Formal analysis, Resources.

Osabohien, Emmanuel: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Validation, Funding acquisition, Resources, Supervision, Project administration.

Diagboya, Paul N.: Writing – original draft/review and editing, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Formal analysis, Resources.

REFERENCES

- Adeyeye, E.I., Olaleye, A.A., Aremu, M.O., Atere, J.O and Idowu, O.T. (2020), Sugar, antinutrient, and food properties levels in raw, fermented and germinated pearl millet grains. *Trends in Science and Technology Journal*, 5(3): 745-758.
- Aremu, M.O., Andrew, C., Oko, O.J., Odoh, R., Ambo, I.A., & Hikon, B.N. (2021), Nutrient, antinutrient and sugar contents in desert date (*Balanites aegyptiaca* (L.) Del) seed and pulp. *International Journal of Science*, 10(7): 13-21.
- Chahopadhyay, S., Raychaudhuri, U. and Chakraborty, R. (2014), Artificial sweeteners – a review, *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 51(4): 611-621.
- Charlton, K., Kowal, P., Sorano, M., Williams, S., Banks, E. (2014), Fruit and vegetable intake and body mass index in a large sample of middle-aged Australian men and women. *Nutrients* 6(6): 2305-2319.
- Gidado A., Daja A., Kassim Z.M., Idris A., and Audu M. (2018), Free Sugars and

- Fructan Contents of Commonly Consumed Fruits of Maiduguri Metropolis North East Nigeria. *J Food process Technol* **10**, 770.
- Hossain, A., Rahman, M., and Shabuz, Z.R. (2012), Quality of industrially processed fruit juices: An assessment using multivariate framework. *Dhaka University Journal of Sciences*, **60(2)**: 169-173.
- Jasmine, Y.S. (2012), Comparison of sugar content in bottles 100% fruit juice versus extracted juice of fresh fruit. *Food and Nutrition Sciences*, **3**, 1509-1513.
- Jhaumeer-Laulloo, S., Rondeau, P., Cadet, F, and Ramasamia, P. (2003), Quantitative determination of sugar in fruits by different methods. *Chemistry: An Indian Journal*, **1**, 131-136.
- Krog-Mikkelsen, I., Hels, O., Tetens, I., Holst, J.J., Anderson, J.R., and Bukhave, K. (2011), The effects of L-arabinose on intestinal sucrose activity: dose-response studies in vitro and in humans. *The American J. Clinical Nutr.*, **94(2)**: 472-478.
- Najwa, F.R. and Azrina, A. (2017), Comparison of vitamin C content in citrus fruits by titration and high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) methods. *International Food Research Journal*, **24(2)**: 726.
- Ndife, J., Awogbenja, D. and Zakari, U. (2013), Comparative evaluation of the nutritional and sensory quality brands of orange juice in Nigeria market. *African Journal of Food Science*, **7(12)**: 479-484.
- Nweze, C.C., Abdulganiyu, M.G. and Erhabor, O.G. (2015), Comparative analysis of Vitamin C in fresh juice of *Malus domestica*, *Citrus sinensi*, *Ananas comosus* and *Citrullus lanatus* by iodometric titration. *International Journal of Science, Environment and Technology*, **4(1)**: 17-22.
- Okiei, W., Ogunlesi, M., Azeez, L., Obakachi. V., Osunsanmi, M., Nkenchor, G. (2009), The Voltammetric and Titrimetric Determination of Ascorbic acid levels in Tropical Fruits sample. *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.* **4**, 276-287.
- Qi, B. (2023), *Impact of exercise training on stress signaling pathway and purine metabolism in healthy and disease models and the influence of ribose supplementation* (Doctoral dissertation, Victoria University).
- Sani, A., Yusuf, A.O., Dennis, O. and Yusuf, I.S. (2015), Comparative Determination of Ascorbic Acid in Some Selected Fruits and Vegetables Commonly Consumed in Northern Nigeria. *J of Global Biosciences*, **4(1)**, 1867-1870.
- Temple, N.J and Gladwin, K.K (2003), fruit, vegetables and the prevention of cancer: research challenges. *Nutrition* **19**, 467-470.
- Wang, A.H and Still, C. (2007), Old world meets modern: a case report of scurvy. *Nutr. Clin. Pract.* **22**, 445-448.
- Wargovich, M. (2000), Anticancer properties of fruits and vegetables. *Horticultural Science*, **3(5)**: 573-575.
- WHO 2003, Diet, nutrition and the prevention of chronic diseases. Report of a Joint FAO/WHO Expert Consultation. Geneva, (WHO Technical Report Series, No.916).
- Wilson, L.D., Fai, F.Y., Buhari, M. and Zainab, I. (2015), Comparative Determination of Vitamin C and Iron in Ten (10) Locally Consumed Fruits in Gombe State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Chemical Science* **2(8)**: 14-18.